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SHARQ GAVHARI XIVA SHAHRIDA MA'MUN UNIVERSITETI NODAVLAT TA'LIM MUASSASASINING FAOLIYATI

O'zbekiston hududida sivilizatsiya va davlatchilikning shakllanishida qadimiy madaniyat o'choqlaridan biri Xorazm muhim o'rin tutgan. Binobarin "O'zbek davlatchiligining tamal toshlari bundan 2700 yil muqaddam ayni Xorazm vohasida qo'yilgan. Shu ma'noda, milliy davlatchiligimiz tarixi Misr, Xitoy, Hindiston, Yunoniston, Eron kabi eng qadimiy davlatlar bilan bir qatorda turadi. Xorazm tarixi o'zbek davlatchiligiga oid ulkan ma'lumotlar, moddiy va yozma yodgorliklar to'plangan tarixni asosi, uning qudrati va qadimiyligining tasdig'idir".

Davlatchilikka asos solinishi uchun, avvalombor, huquqiy asos bo'lishi kerak va shu ma'noda Xorazmda huquq ilmi ham shu davrlarda shakllangan. Shuningdek, Xorazm zaminidan yetishib chiqqan ilm-u fan namoyondalari yaratgan asarlar jahon tamadduni xazinasiga qo'shilgan katta hissa ekanligi barchamizga ma'lum.

Bu borada ayniqsa, XI asr boshida tashkil etilgan Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi (Majlisi ulamo) allomalarining qomusiy ilmiy faoliyati jahon ilm-fani taraqqiyotini yangi pog'onaga ko'taradi, bu faoliyat rakursini kengaytirib yubordi. Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi jahon ilmiy tafakkur tadriji, madaniy va ma'naviy taraqqiyotining benazr durdonasi sifatida tarixda chuqur, o'chmas iz qoldirgan.

Dunyo sivilizatsiyasi tarixida bunday markazlar o'zining mustahkam asoslariga, qadimiy ildizlarga egadir. Jumladan, insoniyat tarixidagi ilk akademiya, Aflotun akademiyasining "Bog' suhbatlari" – olimlarining turli mavzular bo'yicha bahs-munozalar shaklida voqelangan bo'lsa, keyingi davrlardagi ilmiy markazlar olimlarning doimiy ilmiy faoliyati bilan shug'ullanuvchi uyushmalariga aylangan. Ushbu an'analar islom davrida yangi bosqichga ko'tarilgan. IX asrda Bag'dodda tashkil topgan ikkinchi akademiya – "Bayt ul-hikma" Sharqning to'ng'ich akademiyalaridan sanalib, mazkur ilmiy dargohda ijod qilgan olimlarning aksari, jumladan, Muhammad al-Xorazmiy, Ahmad al-Farg'oniy, Ahmad al-Marvaziy, Abbos al-Javhariy va boshqalar Movarounnahr zaminidan yetishib chiqqan taniqli allomalar va mutafakkirlar edi. Ular tomondan yaratilgan bebaho asarlar va ilmiy kashfiyotlar keyinchalik Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi olimlar jamoasining nazariy va amaliy ilmlar sohasida erishgan yutuqlari uchun ma'naviy asos bo'lgan edi.

Tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, O'rta Osiyoda IX asrgacha shahar madaniyati beto'xtov rivojlanib, IX-XII asrlar ushbu o'lka xalqlari uchun buyuk yuksalish davri bo'lgan. Xorazm hukmdorlarining faol harakati tufayli XI asrning ikkinchi yarmida Ma'muniy xorazmshohlar davlati vujudga kelib, mamlakatning siyosiy, iqtisodiy va madaniy jihatdan yuksalishi davri bo'ldi. Ayniqsa, Ma'mun ibn Muhammad (992-997), Ali ibn Ma'mun (997-1009) davrida Xorazmda davlat mustaqilligi mustahkamlanib, uning harbiy qudrati oshdi. 1004-yildan Beruniyning Gurganchga kelishi bilan Xorazmshoh saroyida olimlar davrasi tezlik bilan to'la bordi va bu davrni Ma'mun akademiyasining to'la shakllangan, gullagan davri deyish mumkin. Abu Mansur as-Saolibiyning guvohlik berishicha, Gurganchda to'plangan faqat arabiynavis adiblarning o'zi 200 ga yaqin bo'lgan.

Tarixdan ayonki, vatanimizda taraqqiyotning yangi davri boshlanishi aynan Ma'mun asos solgan va Sharqning mashhur allomalarini bir dargohga jamlab, ularga zarur shart-sharoit, imkoniyat, imtiyozlar yaratib bergan 1004-yildagi "Dorul hikma", "Majlisi ulamo", ya'ni akademiya

tarqalgan ilm nurlaridan boshlanadi. Ma'munning hukmdor sifatidagi, davlat yuritishdagi huquq va siyosatdagi tafakkuri, ilm-fan namoyondalarini ezgu g'oyalar tevaragida birlashtirdi. Bu ezgu g'oya esa ko'p o'tmay jamiyatda o'z natijasini ko'rsatdi va matematika, astronomiya, kimyo, tibbiyot, huquq, geodeziya singari shu davrga xos barcha fanlar rivojlanib, Birinchi renessansga asos bo'ldi. Bunda o'z bag'riga daho mutafakkirlarni to'plagan oliy ma'rifat maskani – Ma'mun akademiyasi muhim rol o'ynagan edi.

Jahon ilm-u fanining e'tirof eshiticha, “Dor-ul hikma va maorif” (Ma'mun akademiyasi) nomini olgan mazkur ilmiy muassasa nafaqat Sharq balki butun dunyo uchun ham ahamiyatga egadir. Zeroki, ushbu dargohda Beruniy (973-1048), Ibn Sino (980-1037), Abu Mansur Ibn Iroq (958-1036), Abu Sahl Masihiy (970-1042), Abul Hayr Ibn Hammor (942-1018), Abu Mansur as-Saolibiy (961-1038), Abu Ali Ibn Miskovayh, (vafoti 1030), Abdulhakim Muhammad ibn Abdulmalik as-Solih, Al-Xorajiy, al-Hamdamiy, abu Abdulloh Al-Biyan Al-Naysaburiy, Ahmad Ibn Muhammad as-Suhayliy al-Xorazmiy, Ahmad ibn Muhammad as-Sahriy, Mahmud Hamid Ibn Xidr al-Xo'jandiy kabi ko'plab fan namoyandalari ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borishgani, tarixiy fakt va ular yaratgan asarlar tamaddun taraqqiyoti tadrijida muhim o'rin egalladi.

Akademiyasi allomalari Yunoniston, Yaqin Sharq va Hindiston, O'rta Sharqda erishilgan ilm-fan yutuqlarini ijodiy, tanqidiy, qiyosiy tahlil qilib, uni yanada yuksak bosqichga ko'tarishgan. Aynan ana shu allomalarning ilmiy faoliyati, asarlari tufayli Qadimgi Xorazmning san'ati, adabiyoti, astronomiyasi, matematikasi, sug'orish madaniyati yutuqlari jahon tamadduni xazinasiga kirgan va butun insoniyat manfaatlariga xizmat qila boshlagan.

Mustaqillik yillarida tarixda chuqur iz qoldirgan tabarruk ilm dargohining qaytadan Xorazm zaminida barpo etilishi dunyo olimlari, ilm-fan jamoatchiligi tomonidan olqishlandi, iliq kutib olindi. YUNESKOning 2004-yilda “Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasining 1000 yilligini nishonlash to'g'risida”gi qarori esa O'zbekiston hududi azaldan ilm-ma'rifat o'chog'i, ziyo markazi bo'lgani, bu an'ana bugun ham davom etayotganining jahoniy e'tirofi bo'ldi, albatta.

Davlatimiz rahbari Shavkat Mirziyoyevning 2017-yil yanvar oyida Xorazm viloyatiga, xususan, Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasiga tashrifi davomida bergan topshiriq va ko'rsatmalari respublikamiz olimlariga ham ko'rsatilgan hurmat-ehtirom namunasidir. Tabiiyki, bu ajdodlarimiz qoldirgan bebaho ilmiy merosdan unumli foydalanish barobarida, ilmiy yangilik va kashfiyotlar qilish, innovatsiyalar yaratish, yoshlarni ilmga jalb etib, iqtidorli, dunyo tan oladigan yagi avlod olimlari yetishtirishga katta ishtiyoq uyg'otadi.

Bugungi kunda Xorazm ramziga aylangan Xiva shahri haqidagi ilk ma'lumotlar X asrga oid arab sayyohlari asarlarida uchrasada XVII asr boshlariga kelib yirik shaharga aylanadi. Xiva xonlari davrida davlatdagi ilm-fan, adabiyot va san'atga qiziqish yanada yuksaladi. Shaharda saroy, hovli, karvonsaroy, masjid, hammomlardan tashqari ilm, ma'rifat ulashguvchi madrasalar, qorixonalar, kichik yoshli bolalar uchun xususiy uy maktabxonalari qurila boshlandi. Bu jarayon, ayniqsa, XVII asrda nihoyatda avj olib, XIX asrda o'zining cho'qqisiga chiqdi. Xiva shahridan tashqari butun xonlik hududida katta va go'zal peshtoqli madrasalar, atrofi bir yo'la ikki qavatli hujralar bilan o'ralgan hovlisi, masjidi va minorasi bo'lgan madrasalar qurildi. Tarixiy ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, XIX asr boshlarida faqat Xiva shahrining o'zida 120 madrasa va 63 qorixona faoliyat olib borgan bo'lib, rus bosqinidan so'ng ular soni 64 taga, 1922-yilga kelib 54 taga kamayganligini ko'rish mumkin. Mazkur madrasalarda islom dini va huquqidan tashqari, arab va fors tillari, tibbiyot, geografiya, musiqashunoslik, falsafa, tabiiy bilimlar kabi dunyoviy fanlar o'rgatilar edi. Madrasalar davlat idoralari uchun mutaxassislar, maktabdor va san'atkorlarni tayyorlab berdi.

Mustaqillik sharofati bilan Xorazmda ilm-fanga bo'lgan e'tibor yaxshilandi. XI asrda faoliyat olib borgan “Majlis ul-ulamo”ning vorisi sifatida Xiva shahrida Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi 1997-yil 11-noyabrda Birinchi Prezidentning maxsus farmoni asosida qayta tashkil qilingan bo'lsa, 2006-yilda uning 1000 yillik yubileyi keng miqyosda nishonlandi. Mazkur tadqiqot muassasasining ochilishi Xorazmda tarix, arxeologiya, manbashunoslik, filologiya, tuproqshunoslik, qishloq xo'jaligi kabi mintaqa uchun zarur bilimlarning rivojiga ta'sir qildi. Jumladan, 2500 yildan ortiq tarixga ega bo'lgan Xumbuztepa arxeologik yodgorligining ochilishi va uning quyi qatlamlari miloddan avvalgi VII-VI asrlarga oidligi isbotlanganining o'zi fikrimizning yaqqol misolidir.

Yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek, ulkan ilmiy meros va tarixga ega bo'lgan Xorazm va uning ajralmas bir qismi hisoblangan Xiva shahrida bugungi kunda ham ilm-fanga e'tibor yildan yilga ortib bormoqda. Xivada tashkil qilingan Ma'mun universiteti ulkan ilmiy salohiyatning mantiqiy davomi sifatida faoliyatini boshlaganiga hali ko'p bo'lgani yo'q.

Dunyo afkor ommasining e'tibor va e'tirofiga ega bo'lgan hamda shu davrda yaratilgan boqiy asarlari bilan hanuz tamaddunga xizmat qilib kelayotgan olimlarni o'z dargohiga to'plagan, ilm-fan homiysi, o'z davrining Metsenati hisoblangan, ma'rifatparvar Ma'mun nomi bilan ataladigan universitet qisqa davr ichida respublikada o'z nufuziga, obro-e'tiboriga ega bo'ldi. Muassasa yildan yilga o'z maqomini mustahkamlab borayotgani kishini quvontiradi.

Ushbu ta'lim dargohi bugungi kunda 7 mingga yaqin talablar tahsil olayotgan, Xiva shahrida faoliyat olib borayotgan dastlabki va hozircha yagona zamonaviy universitet sifatida o'z mustahkam o'rniga ega bo'lib ulgurdi. Bugungi kunda universitetda ikki yuzdan ortiq malakali professor-o'qituvchilar (shundan yuzga yaqini ilmiy darajali) ta'lim jarayonlari bilan bir vaqtda o'zlarining ilmiy faoliyatlarini Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi va boshqa ilmiy tashkilotlar bilan hamnafas, hamkorlikda olib borishmoqda.

Mamlakatda xususiy oliy ta'lim muassasalarining ochilishi nafaqat oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'rtasidagi raqobatni kuchaytirishga, balki hududlarning iqtisodiy ahvoriga ham o'z ta'sirini kuchaytiradi. Xususan, hozirgi kunda Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda 210 ta OTM mavjud bo'lib, undan 65 tasi nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari bo'lsa, 30 tasi xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari va ularning filiallari hisoblanadi. Bundan ko'rishimiz mumkinki, mamlakatimizdagi jami oliy ta'lim muassasalarining deyarli yarmi nodavlat va xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari hissasiga to'g'ri keladi. Bu, albatta, quvonarli holat, ya'ni abituriyentlarga keng tanlov imkoniyati yaratildi. Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi oliy o'quv yurtlari o'rtasida nafaqat talabalarni o'ziga jalb etish uchun raqobatni rivojlantirdi, balki ilmiy salohiyatli va bilimli bo'lgan professor-o'qituvchilarni o'ziga jalb etish bo'yicha ham o'zaro raqobat muhiti shakllandi. Natijada, o'qituvchilik kasbining maqomi oshdi, uning qadri ko'tarildi, ish haqlari oshirildi, ularga bo'lgan munosabat o'zgardi, eng asosiysi, o'qituvchilarda o'z-o'ziga ishonch, kasbiga bo'lgan ichki hurmat tuyg'usi mustahkamlandi, ilmiy tadqiqot olib borish uchun ijodiy muhit sifati yaxshilanib, natijada ishtiyoq oshdi.

Mamlakatimizdagi nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari faoliyat olib borishi uchun yaratilgan sharoitlar va berilayotgan imkoniyatlar natijasida nafaqat poytaxtimizda, balki hududlarda ham nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'z faoliyatini boshladi va buning natijasida hududlarning iqtisodiyoti, aholining turmush darajasi, turizm salohiyati, investitsion jozibadorligi oshdi. Xususan, davlat rahbarimiz boshchiligida ta'lim muassasalari va pedagog-xodimlarga yaratilayotgan sharoitlar va imkoniyatlar natijasida Xorazm viloyatida ham nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi uchun yetarli sharoitlar va imkoniyatlar yaratildi va buning natijasida hozirga kunda viloyatda 3 ta nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari va 1 ta xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasasi filiali faoliyat olib bormoqda.

Ma'mun universiteti viloyatdagi oliy ta'lim muassasalari orasida talabalar kontingenti bo'yicha 2-o'rinda (1-o'rinda UrDU), nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari orasida esa 1-o'rinda turadi. Ma'mun universitetining asosiy binosi viloyat markazidan 30-35 km. masofa uzoqlikda joylashganligiga qaramasdan, hozirgi kunda ushbu universitetda 7 mingdan ortiq talaba kunduzgi va sirtqi ta'lim shakllarida tahsil olib kelmoqda. Yana bir quvonarli tomoni shundaki, universitet talabalari tarkibi nafaqat viloyatimiz aholisidan, balki respublikamizning deyarli barcha hududlari aholisidan tashkil topgan. Viloyatimizda bunday oliy ta'lim muassasasining faoliyat olib borishi nafaqat yoshlarning oliy ta'lim bilan qamrab olish darajasini oshishiga olib keladi, balki ularning bilimi, fikrlashi, dunyoqarashi kengayishiga olib keladi, hududning madaniy-maishiy saviyasiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Hududlarda nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi iqtisodiy jihatdan bevosita o'sha hududning rivojlanishiga, yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmining oshishiga, aholi bandligini oshishiga, aholi turmush tarzining oshishi, hududlarda xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi faoliyati, turizm faoliyatining rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Ma'mun universitetining Xiva shahrida faoliyat olib borishi

natijasida, nafaqat tumanning, balki viloyatning iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy ahvoriga o'zining ijobiy hissasini qo'shib kelmoqda. Jumladan, universitet faoliyat olib borishi natijasida ikki yuz ellikdan ortiq yangi ish o'rinlari ochildi, universitetga har yili 20 dan ortiq xorijlik professor-o'qituvchilarning jalb etilishi natijasida turistik xizmatlar hajmi oshdi, respublikaning boshqa hududlaridan professor-o'qituvchilar va talabalarining jalb etilishi natijasida ichki turizm rivojlandi, hududdagi savdo va xizmat ko'rsatish sohalari deyarli 1,5-2 barobarga oshdi, xorijlik ilmiy salohiyatli olimlarni jalb etish orqali xorijiy mamlakatlar bilan hamkorlik aloqalari rivojlanishiga erishildi.

Eng samarali reklama insonlarning yaqinlariga qilgan reklamasi (jonli reklama) ekanligini hisobga olgan holda, viloyatimizga, universitetimizga tashrif buyurgan har bir mehmonda universitetimiz faoliyati, viloyatimiz, respublikamiz iqtisodiyoti, aholi turmush darajasi, urf-odatlarini, tarixiy obidalarini, bayramlari, ovqatlari haqida ijobiy xulosalarni shakllantirishga erishsak, kelajakda ular nafaqat ta'lim berish uchun, balki o'z yaqinlari bilan birga dam olish maqsadida ham tashrif buyurishlari mumkin.

Universitet oldiga qo'ygan asosiy maqsadlardan biri bu – barcha talabalarni to'liq grant asosida, bepul o'qitish tizimini joriy etish, dunyoning eng rivojlangan oliy o'quv yurtlari mingtaligiga kirish va Ma'mun universiteti brendini yaratish, Ma'mun ta'lim klasterini joriy etish hisoblanadi. Bu borada universitetimizda bir qator ishlab olib borilmoqda va "Ma'mun universiteti-2030" strategiyasi bo'yicha yo'l xaritalari ishlab chiqildi. Bunday natijalarga universitetda "Universitet 3.0" modelini to'liq joriy etish va bosqichma-bosqich "Universitet 4.0" modeliga o'tish orqali erishish rejalashtirilgan.

Ushbu ko'zlangan maqsadlarga erishmaguncha universitet jamoasi izlanishdan, harakatdan, ilm olishdan, ilm o'rgatishdan to'xtamaymiz va rejalarni amaliyotga joriy etish orqali, mamlakatimiz rahbarining, talabalarining, xalqimizning oldidagi majburiyatimizni bajargan va ularning ishonchini oqlagan bo'lamiz.

Barchamizga ma'lumki, har qanday jamiyatning ravnaqi, ijtimoiy, siyosiy, iqtisodiy barqarorligi o'sha yerda istiqomat qiluvchi fuqarolarining aqliy va axloqiy salohiyatining qay darajada rivojlanganligi bilan bog'liq. Zero, jamiyatning ma'naviy kamoloti, ijtimoiy yashash tarzi, kognitiv rivojlanganlik darajasi shu davlatning milliy mentaliteti yuksalishida, shuningdek, kadrlar tayyorlashning milliy masalasida ham ustuvor mezon hisoblanadi. Inson kamolotida, uning farovonligi va shaxsiy manfaatlarini ro'yobga chiqarishda hamda kerakli ijtimoiy xulq-atvor andozalarini shakllantirishda kasbning ahamiyati katta hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, bugungi kunda rivojlanayotgan psixolog mutaxassislariga bo'lgan talab davr talabi sifatida yaqqol namoyon bo'lmoqda. Inson bolasi kamolga yetgani sari ilmga, ma'rifatga talpinadi. Shu nuqtayi nazardan saboqni doimiy ravishda ijtimoiy muhit ta'sirida o'zlashtirib boradi. Bugungi shiddatkor jamiyatda psixolog kasbiga bo'lgan talab aynan inson omili bilan ishlashda, uning ta'sir obyektining butun hayotidagi ahamiyatini hisobga oladigan bo'lsak, shaxs kamolotida turli xil muammolarning yuzaga kelishi va uning yechimi bilan faoliyat olib borishda ko'rinadi.

Jamiyatda shaxsning shakllanishi insonning o'z aqliy qobiliyatlari jismoniy imkoniyatlari u yoki bu sohaga bo'lgan layoqati, qiziqish va intilishlari, shuningdek, qadriyat va dunyoqarashiga ko'ra belgilanar ekan, inson omilining aynan shu jihatlarni shakllanishi va rivojlanishida salbiy omillarning ta'sirini bo'lmasligini cheklay olmaymiz, chunki hayot tarzi turli xillik bilan bog'liqligidan tashqari, inson shaxsi rivojlanishidagi ehtiyojlari, individual psixologik xususiyatlari, atrof-muhit ta'siri kabilar murakkab hayot tarzining dolzarb muammolaridan biridir.

Bu o'rinda Ma'mun universiteti o'z oldiga psixolog kasbiga tayyorlanadigan mutaxassislarni har tomonlama yetuk, eng avvalo, boshqalarga yordam berish ko'nikmasini shakllantirish bilan birga o'z shaxsiy muammolarini oldindan ko'ra bilish va uni hal qila olish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lgan mutaxassislarni tayyorlashni o'z oldiga maqsad qilib qo'ygan. Chunki, inson shaxsida, turli yoshdagi kishilar bo'lgan jamoaviy munosabatlarda, kasbiy faoliyatga moslashish, yangi ijtimoiy rolni tushunib olish har bir inson hayotida yangi muammolarni keltirib chiqarishini hisobga olgan holda bu mezonlarga e'tibor qaratish hamda jahon amaliyotining muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan, shuningdek, zamon talablariga mos keladigan jahon andozalari asosida mutaxassislikka tayyorlashga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev tashabbusi bilan jamiyatimizda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar, tabiiyki inson qadrini oshirish, uning huquq va manfaatlarini himoyasini kuchaytirishdek ezgu maqsadga yo‘naltirilgan. Aynan shu tufayli ham davlat rahbarining siyosiy irodasi bois huquqiy demokratik, adolatli jamiyatda, ilm-u fan rivoji uchun ilmiy-pedagogik jamoalarga zarur shart-sharoit, imkoniyat yaratib berilmoqda. Negaki, davlatimiz rahbari ta’kidlaganlaridek, “Biz o‘z oldimizga mamlakatimizda Uchinchi Renessans poydevorini barpo etishdek ulug‘ maqsadni qo‘ygan ekanmiz, buning uchun yangi xorazmiylar, beruniylar, ibn sinolar, ulug‘beklar, Navoiy va boburlarni tarbiyalab beradigan muhit va sharoitlarni yaratishimiz kerak”, degan da’vatiga hamohang olib borilayotgan tizimli yangilanishlarning amaldagi in’ikosidir.

Agarki tarixdagi jarayonlarga nazar solib, tahlil etadigan bo‘lsak, davlat boshqaruvida olib borilgan odil siyosat, davlatning ilm-ma’rifatga, olimlarga e’tibori, ta’lim-tarbiya ustuvor etib qo‘yilgani o‘tmishdagi Uyg‘onish davriga xos eng muhim jihat bo‘lgan.

Aynan shu ma’noda, so‘nggi yillarda Yangi O‘zbekistonda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarni, ayniqsa, ilm-fan, ta’lim sohadagi innovatsion yangilanishlar, olim va ziyolilarga yaratib berilayotgan shart-sharoitlar, yoshlar ta’lim-tarbiyasi yo‘lida bajarilayotgan beqiyos ishlarni ma’rifatparvar Xorazmshoh Ma’moni ibn Ma’mun, Ali ibn Ma’munning, adolatparvar Sohibqiron Amir Temurning tamoyillariga qiyoslash mumkin. Ya’ni, bugungi davrimizda o‘tmish bilan bugun va kelajak uyg‘unlashgan holda yana Renessanslarga xos tamaddunga zamin yaratilmoqda.

Shu ma’noda Ma’mun universitetining o‘tmishdagi Ma’mun asos solgan, rivoj toptirgan akademiyasi singari dovruc tarqatishi borasidagi o‘z sa’yi harakatlarimizda dadil boraveramiz.

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LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL STUDY OF THE NOVEL “O‘TKAN KUNLAR” AND ITS’ TRANSLATION VERSIONS INTO THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The paper focuses on the linguoculturological study of the translation versions of the uzbek novel “O‘tkan kunlar”. The novel was translated into English for several times. This article is devoted to a comprehensive study of the issues of linguoculturological and cognitive study of the translation through the analysis of Uzbek language units that are taken from the book of “O‘tkan kunlar” by Abdullah Qadiriyy and to reveal how the translators overcome the difficulties encountered in its translation while translating linguocultural texts into the English language. “O‘tkan kunlar” was translated by Carol Ermakova as “Abdulla Qadiri. Days gone by” and this edition was published by the French publishing house Nouveau Monde Editions. Mark Reese translated the novel as “O‘tkan kunlar (Bygone days) by Abdullah Qodiriyy” and this edition was published by Muloqot Cultural Engagement Program. At this point, we express our deep gratitude to the translators for providing us with the translations of such a great work into English. Nowadays, the translation versions are researched in comparative literature, comparative linguistics and translation studies. Comparative study of their translations is also important for future translators. And this article also may be useful for the researchers who are searching new information in the field of the comparative analysis of the linguoculturemes. Because it argues the problems of translating linguocultural units. In fact, “O‘tkan kunlar” discloses the history of the uzbek traditions and customs, lifestyle, characters of the personages. The article explains the linguocultural analysis of the culture-specific items which are specific to the uzbek culture.

Key words: Linguoculturological analysis, source text (ST), source language (SL), target text (TT), target language (TL), culture-specific items, culture-bound words, linguocultureme, equivalence

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“O‘TKAN KUNLAR” ROMANI VA UNING INGLIZ TILI TARJIMALARINING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada “O‘tkan kunlar” romani ingliz tarjima variantlari lingvokulturologik tahlil qilingan. Ma’lumki, ushbu o‘zbek romani ingliz tiliga bir necha bor tarjima qilingan. Maqolada

Abdulla Qodiriyning “O‘tkan kunlar” romanidan olingan o‘zbek tili lingvokulturemalari vositasida tarjimaning lingvokulturologik va kognitiv tadqiqi masalalari har tomonlama o‘rganilgan. Shuningdek, muqobilsiz leksika tarjimasida duch kelinadigan qiyinchiliklar sharhi va ularga tarjimonlar qanday yechim topishi mumkinligi haqidagi fikrlar bayoni keltirilgan. Romanning ingliz tiliga 2 xil tarjima variantlari mavjud bo‘lib, ulardan biri Kerol Yermakova tomonidan “Abdulla Qadiri. Days gone by” deb tarjima qilinib, u Fransiyaning mashhur nashriyoti “Nouveau Monde Editions”da nashr qilingan bo‘lsa, ikkinchisi Mark Riz tomonidan “O‘tkan kunlar (Bygone days) by Abdullah Qodiriy” deb o‘g‘irilgan va u “Muloqot Cultural Engagement Program” dasturi doirasida chop etilgan. Shu o‘rinda har ikkala tarjimonga ham yosh ilmiy izlanuvchilar uchun shunday noyob asarning ingliz tarjima variantlarini taqdim etganliklari uchun chuqur minnatdorchiligimizni izhor etamiz. Hozirda qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog‘ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik ixtisosligi bo‘yicha tarjima asarlar tadqiqi ko‘p kuzatilmoqda. Asar tarjimalarining qiyosiy o‘rganilishi bo‘lajak tarjimonlar va ilmiy izlanuvchilar uchun ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqola lingvokulturemalarni qiyosiy tahlili bo‘yicha yangilik izlayotgan tadqiqotchilar uchun ham foydali bo‘lishi mumkin. Chunki unda lingvomadaniy birliklarni tarjima qilish muammolari muhokama qilinadi. Darhaqiqat, “O‘tkan kunlar” romani o‘zbek xalqi madaniyati, urf-odatlar va an‘analari, tarixi, turmush tarzi, milliy siymolarining xarakterini ochib beradi. Xulosa qilsak, mazkur maqolada o‘zbek xalqi madaniyatiga xos bo‘lgan lingvokulturemalarning lingvokulturologik tahlili yoritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Lingvokulturologik tahlil, aslyat matni, tarjima matni, muqobilsiz leksika, lingvokulturema, ekvivalent.

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ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ РОМАНА «МИНУВШИЕ ДНИ» И ЕГО АНГЛИЙСКИХ ПЕРЕВОДОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье лингвокультурологически анализируются английские переводные варианты романа «Минувшие дни». Известно, что этот узбекский роман несколько раз переводился на английский язык. В статье всесторонне изучаются вопросы лингвокультурологического и когнитивного исследования перевода с помощью лингвокультурных форм узбекского языка, взятых из романа Абдуллы Кадыри «Минувшие дни». Также дается обзор трудностей, возникающих при переводе безальтернативной лексики, и изложение идей о том, как переводчики могут найти их решение. Есть 2 версии романа на английском языке, одна из которых переведенная как «Abdulla Qadiri. Days gone by» Кароля Ермакова, второй роман был переведен Марком Ризом как «O‘tkan kunlar (Bygone days) by Abdullah Qodiriy». На этом этапе мы выражаем глубокую благодарность обоим переводчикам за предоставление английских переводов такой уникальной работы для молодых исследователей. В настоящее время широко наблюдается изучение переводных произведений в области сравнительного литературоведения, лингвистики, переводоведения. Сравнительное изучение переводов произведений важно для будущих переводчиков и исследователей. Данная статья также может быть полезна исследователям, интересующимся новым и сравнительным анализом языковой культуры благодаря обсуждению проблемы перевода лингвокультурных единиц. Действительно, роман «Минувшие дни» раскрывает культуру, обычаи и традиции, историю, образ жизни, характер национальных деятелей узбекского народа. В данной статье проводится лингвокультурологический анализ лингвокультур, характерных для культуры узбекского народа.

Ключевые слова: Лингвистический анализ, оригинальный текст, переведенный текст, безальтернативные лексиконы, лингвокультуры, эквивалент.

INTRODUCTION.

The text of the culture causes difficulties for the translators. As culture shows the complex background of the language. Culture considers as an essential element of the language that gives the cultural information of the nation. The present study collects a group of typical Uzbek culture-specific words and analysed them linguoculturally. As an example, it gives opinions of some linguists about the linguoculturemes, translation process and starts with a linguocultural analysis of the culture-bound words which are taken from the translation versions of “O‘tkan kunlar”. It continues with some analysis of the passages from the translation versions of Abdulla Qadiri’s “O‘tkan kunlar”.

Today, the emergence of the linguoculturological analysis of the text is considered a trend in linguistics. Because much research is being done in this field. However, Uzbek culture-specific words have not yet been studied linguoculturologically. That’s why this issue requires further research. We also considered it appropriate to analyze the novel “O‘tkan kunlar” by Uzbek writer Abdulla Qodiriy and its translation versions into English that have been translated successfully by the translators. They give us a great chance to analyse Uzbek literature. Now we can describe Uzbek life, traditions all over the world. Because the novel consists of the words, phrases and expressions which show the national characteristics, national colors of the nation and customs, traditions that related to its way of life.

In view of the fact that the number of existing translation definitions are immense. One of them is that translation is producing a target text in one language, based on a source text in another language. This process is considered one of the very complicated one. Because it involves the comprehension process of a text in one language at first and then the production of that text in another language. It requires switching or processes of transfer between the two languages. And when historical time is factored in the source text, producing target one poses several problems to the translators. Most historical items of any language possess culture-bound words. Sometimes they are associated with equivalent-lacking words or culturally loaded words, realia. As a language is partly the repository and reflection of a culture. Possibly, the most ancient features of the culture lie in the lexis of a language. [1; 183] And the translation is the process which aims at conveying a message between the languages and often accompanies by many linguistic problems such as translating culture-bound words which denote objects of one ethnic culture. It is a complicated process and causes many difficulties to translators.

According to Bassnett & Lefevere, translation is primarily contextual. It is a fact of history and a product of the target culture, and as such it cannot be explained through the mapping of linguistic correspondence between languages, or judged with respect to universal standards of quality and accuracy. [2; 3]

The source texts which are based on the culture-bound items cause problems for translators. Particularly if there are notable differences between the source and target cultures. Because culture-bound items have ethnic and historical peculiarities of one nation’s language which own its culture. There are several strategies which are used for translating equivalent-lacking words in the translation process. They are transcription, transliteration, calque translation, lexical substitution, explicatory translation. Each strategy has its own advantages and disadvantages. And only explicatory translation reveals a culture-bound words meaning in full. Explication of these words can be made in footnotes. Nida has rightfully contended that translated messages are more comprehensible if “drawn out” by the addition of a certain amount of redundancy. [3; 131]

As Mark Shuttleworth & Moira Cowie mentioned that translation have long been paying attention to the translation problem of culture-bound words. And explicatory translation is used one of the useful strategy of translating equivalent-lacking words of the source text. Because explication leads to target text stating source text information in a more explicit form than the original. Translator fills out source text by including additional explanatory phrases, spelling out implicatures or adding connectives to “help” the logical flow of the text and to increase readability. This process may be motivated by the translator’s conscious desire to explain the meaning to the TT reader, or may sometimes simply be an inevitable result of the act of mediation. However, whatever the reason, the result is that “the translator simply expands the TL text, building into it a semantic redundancy absent

in the original”. So explicatory translation prevents lack of understanding culture-bound words or misunderstanding them by the target language readers[4; 55].

METHODS AND THE LEVEL OF STUDY.

Methods of this paper are concerned with the problems of translating linguocultural units. Culture is the way of life. People can't live without culture. Because various traditions and occasions, which people celebrate, are considered culture of the nations. And there are a lot of countries with the people of different nationalities in the world. Each nation owns its culture. Therefore culture also differs. People can get information about each other's culture through the translation. But translating literary texts which have cultural values of the original language create problems for the translators. The task of the translator is not to copy what is said. An interpreter who only reproduces the words and sentences of the source text in the target one finds difficulties during translation process. Because there are no languages around the world which are similar. That's why what an interpreter has to reproduce is not what is said in exact terms.

H.G.Gadamer writes about translating and reading translations from foreign languages. The translator has a linguistic text before him, that is, something said either verbally or in writing, that he has to translate into his own language. He is bound by what stands there, and yet he cannot simply convert what is said out of the foreign language into his own without himself becoming again the one saying it. But this means he must gain for himself the infinite space of the saying that corresponds to what is said in the foreign language. [5; 67]

Mildred L. Larson has rightfully contended that translation is the process of studying the lexicon, the grammatical structure, and the communication situation of the source language text, analyzing it in order to determine the meaning, and then reconstructing this same meaning using the natural forms of the receptor language. While translating the lexicon of the two languages will not match. This mismatch will make it necessary for the translator to make many adjustments in the process of translation. [6; 169]

The difficulties of the translation are often highlighted when there is the context consisting of the cultural item in the translation process. The translator looks for lexical equivalents between the source language and the receptor language which is considered complicated process of the translation. Here some cultural words become untranslatable because of the cultural difference. They are called non-equivalent words which are one type of the linguocultureme.

Peter Newmark has made much of the concept of the untranslatable words. He writes that “to write off as “untranslatable” a word whose meaning cannot be rendered literally and precisely by another word is absurd, particularly when it could at least be better delineated by componential analysis into four or five words, though as a footnote, not in the text of the play.” [7; 79]

While translating untranslatable that is non-equivalent word of the source language, translators have to learn linguoculturemes of the target language. As a result, translation and linguoculturology join together. Linguoculturology finds the answer for this question of the translator: “What is the meaning of the untranslatable word?” The main problem of the non-equivalent word is its meaning.

According to Said Faiq, misunderstandings of the translation generally occur in particular social structures, particular histories, and prevailing norms of language production and reception. He writes that culture involves the beliefs and values, history and national traditions of the particular social groups. In translation the relationship between language and culture is very important. [8;1]

This complex relationship arises while dealing with the translation of the culture-specific words, the so-called realia. This phenomenon reveals the customs and traditions of the original text. Realia has no equivalent word or expression in the target text. In the absence of equivalents, translators use the process of transliteration, which changes the form of the culture-specific word according to the alphabet rules of the target language. This word becomes unknown for the target text readership. Therefore, translators usually explain it with additional information, with footnotes or endnotes. As a result of the transliteration, this realia becomes borrowing in the TL.

According to Geertz, culture is to society what memory is to the person. It specifies designs for living that have proven effective in the past, ways of dealing with social situations, and ways to think

about the self and social behavior that have been reinforced in the past. Geertz considers that culture is connected with the history, the past times of each society. [9; 12]

And Triandis has rightfully contended that when a person is socialized in a given culture, the person can use custom as a substitute for thought, and save time. Triandis suggests that celebrating customs express the life of the people. Each custom is devoted to one occasion in every society. It means that the people around the world understand the use of the customs which are performed in their countries. [10; 20] For example, when Uzbek people say *Non sindirish*, the meaning and the use of this rite is clear to every person who lives in Uzbekistan. After hearing the name of this custom it doesn't require to use the thoughts to express how this custom is celebrated in Uzbek life. As everyone knows about this celebration because of the culture. It means that there is no need to explain the ceremony to the person who lives with you in one country, because he or she can understand it just by hearing the name of every custom, and from this point of view culture can save the time of the people also.

By the beginning of the 21st century, linguoculturology has become one of the leading disciplines in world linguistics. V.A. Maslova writes: "Linguoculturology is a science that studies the language both synchronously and diachronically. The object of the linguoculturology is linguocultural feature of the language of a particular people." And a linguocultureme contains linguocultural feature of the language. [11; 20]

V.V. Vorobev introduces the concept of linguocultureme in science as the main unit of the linguocultural analysis. [12; 44] Linguoculturemes reflect a part of a culture. They may be the words, phraseological units, sentences, texts, speech clichés, folklore texts, compound words, and so on. The main point is that they have to contain cultural importance of the language. If there is no cultural value in the mentioned list, so they are not considered as linguoculturemes.

V.A. Maslova states that there are 9 types of linguoculturemes. (Table I) They are non-equivalent words, mythological language units, the paremiological fund of a language, phraseological fund of a language, stereotypes, metaphors, stylistic content of a language, verbal behavior and speech etiquette. [13; 332]

Table I

<i>Non-equivalent words</i>	<i>Linguoculturemes</i>	<i>Mythological language units</i>
<i>The paremiological fund of a language</i>		<i>Phraseological fund of a language</i>
<i>Stereotypes</i>		<i>Metaphors</i>
<i>Stylistic content of a language</i>		<i>Verbal behavior</i>
<i>Speech etiquette</i>		

The process of linguocultural analysis in the translation between different languages includes the following steps (Table II):

1. Identification of the linguocultural units of the source text. Because cultural phenomenon contains cultural information of any language.
2. Analysis of the cultural information. This process is called linguocultural analysis. Here cultural values of the original text are compared to the culture of the target one and international cultural comparison leads to the interpretation of language as a means of reflecting culture. In order to compare cultural values of the various languages, it is necessary to study cultural space of the translation, which creates problems for the translator, by identifying the units that are considered cultural phenomena. Anyway translators solve this problem. And this phenomenon which shows cultural values of the any aspect of the language is called linguocultureme.

Table II

<i>The process of linguocultural analysis includes:</i>	<i>I Step: Identification of the linguocultural units of the source text. Because cultural phenomenon contains cultural information of any language.</i>
	<i>II Step: Analysis of the cultural information.</i>

As E. Sapir points out, language is a guiding tool in the study of culture. While learning a language, it is necessary to know not only the words but also the culture, customs and traditions of that country. And this process has led to the evolution of the linguocultural studies. [14; 259]

According to H.G. Gadamer, no translation is as understandable as the original. So no translation can replace the original which owns cultural values of the nation. Because the language of the culture which is spoken by the people of the original text differs from the culture of the target one. And here finding lexical equivalent for the culture-specific word makes difficulty for the translators. The cultural value of the source text that has no equivalent in the target language is called linguocultureme. Linguocultureme is a unit of language which reflects culture in its meaning. [5; 68]

Linguoculturological research includes the following issues (Table III): 1. Linguoculturological features of a language. It often deals with the language of folklore and myths; 2. The study of the linguocultural concept of the language fiction; 3. The study of the cultural units in a comparative work. In this case, cultural words, mainly in Uzbek, are compared with English; and this article is devoted to the linguoculturological research which is based on the translated texts which contain cultural values of Uzbek nation. Non-equivalent word *nikah* is the main point of our linguocultural analysis. The following example is presented just for demonstration purposes, without any evaluating aim on translation choices.

Table III

<i>Linguoculturological research includes:</i>	<i>1. Linguoculturological features of a language. It often deals with the language of folklore and myths;</i>
	<i>2. The study of the linguocultural concept of the language fiction;</i>
	<i>3. The study of the cultural units in a comparative work.</i>

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

The term equivalence is used by many writers to describe the nature and the extent of the relationships which exist between SL and TL texts or smaller linguistic units. J.C. Catford has rightfully contended that if the situational features of the SL common to the contextual meanings of the TL text, as a result the better translation can be appear. For that the translators have to choose TL equivalents not with “the same meaning” as the SL items, but with the greatest possible overlap of situational range. And special problems of translation arise when the situation contains elements relevant to the SL text, but absent from the cultural context of the TL. It means that for translation equivalence to occur, SL and TL items must be relatable to at least some of the same situational features of the text. According to J. C. Catford, in order to generalize the conditions of translation equivalence translator has to examine elements or situational features of the text more closely. Because source language and target language items rarely have “the same meaning” in the linguistic sense. But they can function in the same situation. [15; 49]

In addition to the opinions of the scholars mentioned above, we found it permissible to analyze English translation versions of Abdullah Qadiriy’s novel “O‘tkan kunlar”.

The Linguoculturological analysis of the Uzbek Culture-Bound Words *Taksir* and *O‘rda*

In the chapter “Bloody clouds over Tashkent” in the 6 the chapter of “O’tkan kunlar”, if we look at a piece of the text describing the day when Azizbek was meeting with the people, the original passage is given as follows: “Azizbek *o’rda darbozasig’a* osilg’an *ikki gavdani* ko’rsatib so’radi: “Fuqaro! Ko’rasizmi bu *ikki gunohkorni*, nima uchun bu jazog’a mustahiq bo’ldilar?” Xalq: “Bilmaymiz, *taqsir*. ”Azizbekning o’zi javob berdi: “Bular Musulmon cho’loqni sarkardalaridan, qipchoqlarning yo’lboshchilaridan va qora choponning dushmanlaridan bo’lgan *ikki to’ng’izning* gavdalari! Men bularni siz *qora chopon* fuqarom tomonidan o’ch uchun o’ldirdim, siz qora chopon og’aynilarimning qipchoq qo’lida shahid bo’lg’an qarindoshlaringizning ruhlarini shodlantirmoq uchun o’ldirdim! Yoki bu harakatim adolatdan emasmi, fuqaro!” Xalq javob berdi: “*Adolat!* Xo’b qilg’ansiz, *taqsir!* Qipchoqlarning jazolari shunday bo’lmog’i kerak!”” [16; 35]

Now let us pay attention to the text given in Carol Ermakova’s translation version: “Azizbek pointed to *the corpses* hanging from the *court gates* and asked: “*Subjects!* Do you see these criminals? Do you know why they deserved such punishment?” The people replied: “We know not, *milord.*” Azizbek himself answered: “These are the *corpses of two pigs*, Musulman Kul-the Lame’s generals, leaders of the Kipchaks and enemies of the Karachapans! I executed them, avenging you, my loyal Karachapans! I cut them down that the souls of our Karachapan friends slaughtered by the Kipchaks might rejoice! Or did I act unjustly, *my subjects?*” The people swayed, crying out as one: “*Justly, justly!* You acted rightly, *taksyr!* Just so must the Kipchaks be punished!”” [17; 39]

Let us now turn our attention to the following text translated by Mark Reese: “Displaying *two bodies* hung from the *orda gate*, Azizbek asked the people, “Dear *citizens*, do you see these two found *guilty?* Why has this verdict fallen upon them? Why was it visited upon them in this manner?” The people replied, “We don’t know, *master!*” Azizbek answered his own question: “Here are the bodies of *two bastards*, soldiers of Musulman the Lame, leaders of the Qipchaqs and the enemies of all Qora Chopans! I executed them as revenge on behalf of my Black Robe citizens, to bless the martyred spirits of your Black Robe brothers who died by the hands of the Qipchaqs. Are not my actions justified, *my people?*” The people answered, “They are just, *it is justice!* You defended us, *Taksir.* All Qipchaqs should likewise be punished!”” [18; 55]

We witness the Uzbek word *taqsir* is translated into English in different versions as *milord*, *master*, *taksyr* and *taksir*. And we can see that this linguistic unit is used twice in the original text, at the beginning and at the end of the text. But it is translated differently by both translators and they used various equivalents each time. Actually, *taqsir* is an old Uzbek language word that means addressing respectfully to officials, rich and mullahs which is very common in Uzbek culture. [19; 39]

At the beginning of the text Carol Ermakova translated it as *lord* which has the following meaning in English: *a nobleman; the title of certain peers or high officials; a master or ruler.* [22; 301]

Translator wanted to describe this linguistic unit for foreign reader by using the most appropriate equivalent which can be suitable for the translation of it, whereas the word is not used in English at all! And the reason is cultural difference which exist between various languages and customs. Mark Reese translated it as *master* at the beginning of the text which means *a man who has control of people or things* in English and then gave an equivalent as *taksir* at the end of the text. In our opinion, at the beginning of the text both translators translated based on their national mentality for giving better explanation of the word *taqsir* for the readers of the foreign culture. And in this way translators were able to find a phrase that was semantically equivalent to it. At the end of the text both translators transliterated the word as *taksyr* and *taksir*. Here they kept cultural importance of the word and wanted to be acquainted it with the foreign readers all over the world by translating into English language.

As Zoya Proshina has suggested that source language words and target language words may interact in different ways. The words may be monoequivalents, where an equivalent of the source language word can consist of one word or be a phrase in target language as a result of the translation process. A monoequivalent is a regular equivalent of the source language word that consist of one word or be a phrase. Mostly, regular equivalents are terms or proper names. [21; 109]

And the following words which are given in the text are considered monoequivalents, because it is easy to find foreign counterparts of them: *adolat - justice, jazo - punishment, gunohkor - criminal, o'ch olmoq - avenge, xalq - the people*. It is difficult to find linguocultural importance of the words, because they are ordinary words that are appropriate and used in the life of each nation. Multi-equivalents are variable equivalents, which means that to translate a source language word one has to make choice of the equivalents having the same meaning. Multi-equivalents can be monosemantic. For example, Carol Ermakova translated the word *gavda* as *corpse* which means *the body of a dead person* in English, while Mark Reese give an equivalent of the word as *body* which means the whole physical structure of a person or animal, including the head, arms, and legs. [22; 143]

In our opinion semantically translation equivalent of the word *corpse* is correct in this text. Because the speech is about the dead people's bodies which are hung from the *orda* gate to show to the public. There is the word *orda* which has cultural importance in Uzbek history. Carol Ermakova translated it as *court* which means *the place where a king or queen lives and works*. [22; 320]

And Mark Reese tried to keep an originality of the form and meaning of the linguistic unit by transliterating it as *orda*. In Uzbek *orda* means *a residence of the khan, ruler, fortress in the Turkic and Mongolian peoples*. [19; 163]

It also has the meaning of *military headquarters, barracks*. [19; 163] Next word is *fuqaro*. It is translated as *citizen* and *subjects*. The word *subject* is polysemous in English. Because it has the following meanings in English dictionary of Macmillan: 1. *An idea, problem, situation etc that you discuss or write about*. 2. *Something you learn or teach in a school, for example English, mathematics, or biology*. 3. *Linguistics. In English grammar, the person, place, or thing that does what the verb describes*. 4. *A person or animal that is used in a medical or scientific test*. 5. *A person or thing that is shown in a photograph, painting, or piece of art*. 6. *Someone who lives in a country that is controlled by a king or queen*. [22; 1430] and the last meaning of the word can be an equivalent for the word *fuqaro* in the original text. In the translation into English both translators introduced Uzbek words to English world. They tried to increase the reader's interest even more by transliterating Uzbek linguistic units into English, especially the words which were used in the history of Uzbek people. While reading translation versions foreign readers learn new words of Uzbek language which lurk cultural importance of the Uzbek nation. Keeping an original form partially by transliterating them also depend on the skill of the translator.

Linguoculturological analysis of the word “*Otin*” that is used in the Novel “*O'tkan kunlar*”

The next culture-bound word is “*otin*”. The source text of Abdulla Qodiriy is as following “Oftob oyim to'rga harakat qilsa ham, Kumush boshqa mehmonlardan uyalib to'xtadi, O'zbek oyim uni qistab tushdi: - Iymanma, Kumush *otin*, bu kun-erta bizga yangi kelinsan, uchunchi kundan boshlab sen mug'ombirning boshingda tegirmon yurgizishni o'zim yaxshi bilaman! – dedi.” [16; 322] Carol Ermakova translated as “Although Oftobayim sat down, Kumush stopped, hesitating shyly in front of the other guests. “Don't be shy, Kumush-*atyn*,” Uzbekayim insisted. “For today and tomorrow you are our guest, my dear, our new daughter-in-law, then after three days, I shall turn grindstones on your head, you sly girl!”” [17; 287] Carol Ermakova translated the word as “*atyn*” and gave explanation as “*Denotes respect when used with the proper name*” in her Translator's notes which is given at the bottom of each page where culture-bound words used. Mark Reese translated it as “*khotin*”. Reader can see it in the target text as “While Oftob Oyim took her place, Kumush, bashful in front of the other guests, remained still. Uzbek Oyim now pleaded to her, “Don't be shy, Kumush *Khotin*. For today and tomorrow you are our guest as our new bride and, three days from now, I will grind even your pretty little head under the millstone!” She laughed.” [18; 347] In explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language which is named “*O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati*”, the word “*otin*” means the following meanings: “1. Girls' teacher in old schools. Who knows the Shariat well. 2. A woman who heads religious ceremonies as *mawlud* among women. 3. Any educated or teaching woman. 4. A word that can be used in an appeal to educated, respected women or when talking about them, adding it to their name.” [19, 155] Carol Ermakova used the meaning which is explained in sentence 4 and fully delivered the information about the culture-bound word “*otin*”.

Mark Reese gave a definition to the word “*xotin*” as “*woman*” when giving explanation of the word “*hotinboz*”. [18; 423] And he didn’t give extra information in his endnotes about the word *khotin* while using this word instead of the word “*otin*” in translation. Actually the word “*xotin*” in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language has the following meaning: “1. Sexually contrary to the male category, a person with the ability to have children, breastfeed. Woman. 2. Woman in a male marriage”. [19; 415] According to the use of this meaning of the word “*khotin*” instead of the word “*otin*”, the translation version of Mark Reese has lost cultural importance of the word “*otin*”.

Linguocultural analysis of the muslim wedding ceremony “Nikah” and the culture-specific words *mullah*, *khutba*, *mahr*, *yanga* in the translation versions of “O’tkan kunlar”

The paper examines linguocultural analysis of the word *nikah*. The objective of the study is to reveal national and cultural characteristics of the *nikah* in Uzbek weddings by means of their linguocultural analysis. *Nikah* expresses cultural peculiarities of the Uzbek people, considers as a part of the Uzbek wedding ceremony. The results of the investigation can be effectively used for a further linguocultural analysis of Uzbek culture-specific words.

Before analyzing the word *nikah* linguoculturally, it is necessary to state that religion is an important aspect of life in Uzbekistan. Thus, people follow the tradition of *nikah* before the wedding. Muslim marriage ceremony differs from the wedding ceremonies of the other religions. Marriage in Islam is a contract between two people, a groom and a bride, to live together with their own free wills. In Uzbek families, a wedding will not hold without *nikah*. Many people are confused about the difference between marriage and *nikah*. *Nikah* is the religious ceremony of the marriage contract. A *mullah* will read from the Holy Quran and give a short sermon known as a *khutba*. Mark Reese explains *khutba* as traditional sermon delivered by a *mullah* at Friday prayers or a special ceremony. [18; 445]

Mark Reese writes that the chapter of the novel which is called “An unexpected happiness” posed some complications for the translator and editors. The first half of the chapter occurs in present continuous, abruptly switching to past tense halfway through the narration. Qodiriy was attempting to depict a customary wedding in a way that would be credible to Central Asians, he used precepts within Islamic Law as part of the narration style. Islamic Law states that the bride and her witnesses, *the Yangas*, must affirm the marriage contract with “I gave in marriage,” with the groom and his witnesses replaying: “I have accepted”. This part of the wedding ceremony would be referred to as the *Nikoh* – the actual acceptance by the husband of his new bride. [18; 445] Look at the following passage: *Abdulla Qodiriy*: Kumushbibidan vakolat olish ham juda qiyin bo’ldi. *Domlaning*: Sizkim Kumushbibi Mirzakarim qizi, o’zingizni toshkandlik, musulmon Otabek Yusufbek hoji o’g’liga bag’ishlamoq vakolatini amakingiz Muhammadrahim Yo’ldosh o’g’liga topshirdingizmi? Degan so’rog’i olti, yetti qaytarilg’andan keyin, shunda ham *yangalar* qistog’i ostida arang uning rizolig’i olindi. [16; 57] The target text where the word *yanga* is transliterated by Mark Reese: “It was difficult to get Kumush to agree. *The mullah* repeated the question six or seven times: “Will you, Kumush Bibi, the daughter of Mirza Karim, give your authority to Muhammad Rahim, son of Yuldosh, your uncle, to offer your hand in marriage to Otabek, son of Yusufbek Hajji, a devout Muslim from Tashkent? Do you agree to this?” she finally acquiesced, though only after her *yangas* pressured her to accept.” [18; 78] Mark Reese explains the word *yanga* as: ““Sister-in-law” or “wife of an elder brother”, but here we could consider them also witnesses to the consummation of the marriage and protectors of tradition and values.” [18; 442]

Carol Ermakova gives English equivalent of the word *yanga* as *matchmaker*: “Obtaining the bride’s agreement to the marriage turned out to be quite a tricky task; *the mullah* had to repeat his question several times: “Did you, Kumush-bibi, daughter of Mirzakarim, charge your uncle Mohammed Rakhim, son of Yuldash, to give you as wife to this Muslim from Tashkent, Otabek, son of Yusufbek-hadji?” Only after the question had been asked six or seven times and only at the prompting of the *matchmakers*, did they manage to obtain Kumush’s reluctant agreement. [17; 60]

During the *nikah*, the groom gives *mahr*, the gift, to the bride. *Mahr* can be money or gold jewellery. Mark Reese gives explanation of the word *mahr* in the endnotes as “bride price”. [18; 445] Actually it can be anything that the bride desires. In Uzbek marriage usually ring is used as a gift.

There is the text where the word *mahr* is used in the original passage. Abdulla Qodiriy: “Ko’b tortishqandan so’ng quyidag’I mablag’lar mahr qilib belgulanadirlar...” [16; 58] Carol Ermakova translated this text as: Once the young lads had brought Atabek before the mullah, the negotiations with representatives of the groom’s side began. Ziya-shakhichi (acting in place of the father) was negotiating for the groom, and Muhammed Rakhim for the bride. They were discussing *the property* the groom should give his future wife, in full ownership. After a prolonged negotiation, the following *agreement* was reached: the bride would receive three hundred gold tilla; the groom would pledge to buy a spacious house in Margilan after the wedding; one milking cow, household goods ... Once Atabek had agreed to all these terms, the mullah moved on to performing the *nikhoh* rite. As is customary in Islam, he read the prayer exalting Allah, and the prayers honouring the prophet and, finally, he arrived at the most delicate question: “Atabek, son of Yusufbek-hadji, do you agree to take as your wife in sharia, Kumush, daughter of Mirzakarim?” he asked in Farsi. [17; 60] Carol Ermakova can give linguocultural importance of this passage successfully. She translates *mahr* as “*the property*”. After *nikah* the groom and bride are considered religiously married. The mullah proclaims praises to Allah, with upturned hands, all participants proclaim “Amen” and with that the marriage ritual will be over. All the recited prayers are for the happiness of bride and groom.

While translating culture-bound words of “O’tkan kunlar”, translators Carol Ermakova and Mark Reese used efficiently explicatory translation strategy by giving footnotes of equivalent-lacking words which describe Uzbek culture and traditions. Translators added several lines explaining to English readers the significance of realiae of Uzbek culture words. For example, the word “*nikoh*”. The source text of Abdulla Qodiriy is “*To’y bilan nikohni bu kunga qilg’animiz yaxshi bo’ldi*”. [16; 226] Here English readers can understand the word wedding, but not *nikah*. *Nikah* is a contract between two people in Islam. Both the groom and the bride should be agreed to the marriage with their own free wills. Then *mahr* in the form of money or anything agreed upon by the bride such as jewelry, furniture or any kind of possession paid by the groom at the time of marriage. When a *mahr* and contract are agreed upon, after that an Islamic marriage ceremony, wedding, can take place. Carol Ermakova translated this culture-bound word as “*nikokh*” in the TT as following “*It’s good we decided today to hold everything all at once – the nikokh and the wedding*”. [17; 206] Carol Ermakove didn’t give explanation for this word. But Mark Reese translated this word as “*nikah*” in the target message and gave an explanation as “Muslim wedding ceremony” in his endnotes which are given at the end of the book as a unit for explanation of the culture-bound words of Uzbek culture. [18; 466] And the full target message is as following “*We made a good decision by planning nikah and wedding celebrations for the same day.*” [18; 248] Look at the following passage:

Abdulla Qadiri: Nihoyat, yuz adimcha borgandan so’ng, ulardan so’z eshitishka to’g’ri keldi; birisi ikkinchisiga dedi: - *To’y bilan nikohni bu kunga qilg’animiz yaxshi bo’ldi*. – Nima, juvonga ham to’y boshqa, *nikoh* boshqa bo’larmidi? *Bordi-keldi bitta juvon qizi bor-ku*, munga to’yni boshqa, *nikohni* boshqa qilamiz deganiga hayronman. – Axir qutidor ham boobro’ odam-da, - dedi birinchi kishi. [16; 226]

Carol Ermakova: It was only after they had gone ten paces that one said to the other: “It’s good we decided today to hold everything all at once – *the nikokh and the wedding*.” “Well, why celebrate them separately? *After all, she is no maiden. It’s only young girls who celebrate the nikokh and the wedding feast. She has already been wed*. Indeed, it is a wonder her father demanded we mark the *nikokh* and the wedding separately.” “Do not forget, *Kutidor* is a respected citizen here,” countered the first. [17; 206]

Mark Reese: Finally, after a hundred paces, he succeeded in catching a couple of words between them. One said to the other, “We made a good decision by planning *nikah* and *wedding* celebrations for the same day.” “Why should we set a separate engagement date for a divorced woman? *She is not a virgin anymore. Only first-time brides have separate engagement and wedding celebrations*. I am surprised the father insisted on celebrating them separately.” “But *Qutidor* is well respected in this town.” [18; 248]

There is the passage in the ST: “*To’y bilan nikohni bu kunga qilg’animiz yaxshi bo’ldi*”. *To’y* means *wedding* in English, but what about *nikah*? Is *nikah* known for the readership of the TL? As

we mentioned above, some words which show cultural importance of the nation cause difficulties for the translators. They use various methods of translation to avoid this misunderstanding of the translation. Transliteration is the best way of giving cultural words in the target text, because in some cases culture-bound items will not change its form in the receptor language. Because they show the identity of the nation's culture. They are specific only to the place where they used. Therefore, literary translators have to work not only with the source and target languages, but with the cultures too. They can choose several different procedures to deal with this problem. As a result, they present the identity of the source text in the target language.

In the English translation versions of Abdulla Qadiri's "O'tkan kunlar" by Carol Ermakova and Mark Reese, there is the word *nikah* which is used several times in the novel. Translators gave the transliteration of *nikoh* as *nikokh* and *nikah*. [18; 466] *Nikah* shows the cultural identity of Uzbek marriage and its culture. Culture has a significant impact on the identity. Here our understanding of identity means the culture of a nation. As Peter Newmark mentioned, translator's intention is to produce the same effect on his readership as was produced on the readership of the original. As there is much cultural overlap, this is theoretically possible. An English readership would however be unlikely to react like an Uzbek readership to this text and one assumes that the translator should attempt to make his readership envious. The translators show aware of the importance of achieving a strong emotive effect. [7; 278]

In sum, when an equivalent is not found in the TL, translators interpret this word into their native language in the content of the foreign word. The linguoculturological research of the culture-specific word *nikah* reveals that the simpler solution for translating this realia is transliteration and giving explanation in the footnote or endnote. (Table 4.) In the given table you can see the words which are difficult to translate because of the cultural difference of the Uzbek and English languages, and how the translators deal with these words in the translation versions of the novel:

Table IV

Uzbek source language	English target language	
<i>Abdulla Qodiriy</i>	<i>Carol Ermakova</i>	<i>Mark Reese</i>
Nikoh [16; 58]	Nikhoh [17; 61]	Nikah [18; 80]
Yanga [16; 57]	Matchmaker [17; 60]	Yanga [18; 78]
Xutba [16; 58]	Performing the nikhoh rite [17; 61]	Khutba [18; 79]
Domla [16; 58]	The mullah [17; 61]	The mullah [18; 78]
Omin [16; 58]	Amen [17; 61]	Amen [18; 80]
Mahr [16; 58]	The property [17; 60]	Mahr [18;79]
Salovot [16; 58]	The prayers honouring the prophet [17; 61]	Salawat [18;79]

Linguoculturological analysis of the Uzbek national custom named *Fatiha-tui*, *Non Sindirish* and an importance of *Nan*

The linguoculturological study of the Uzbek national custom, which is called "Fatiha-Tui", is devoted to investigate how nan plays an important role in Uzbek culture. Before explaining linguocultural importance of the ceremony Fatiha-Tui, firstly we have to give definition of the *nan*. Because it is connected with the *nan* (naan) of Uzbek people. Nan is a flat bread, typically eaten with South Asian food. This kind of flat bread is called "non" in Uzbek language. And even a small piece of nan is respected in Uzbekistan. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, it is stated that the word "non" comes from, that is originated from the Persian word and means bread, flatbread, food. [19; 57] There are many types of bread in the world. But they differ from country to country. That means the culture of each society has its own form of the bread. It may be known to all nations that the bread is made from dough and it is cooked on the stove or in a pan. But in Uzbek culture it is baked in the tandoor. Tandoor is a device which is used instead of oven in South Asia. It is made of clay, that is thick, heavy soil which is soft when it is wet and becomes hard when it dries or baked, used for making the tandoor. Tandoor is used for cooking and preparing bread, somsa, kebab, etc.

[19; 662] Tandoor was built in every household in former times. Nowadays one can see the tandoor only in the rural areas far from the city in Uzbekistan. It is too difficult to find the tandoor in the households of foreign countries. Because this type of tandoor is specific only to the South Asia countries, especially Uzbek culture.

Now, let us to introduce a national custom which is connected with *nan*. It is called Fatiha-Tui. In Uzbek culture, usually parents, especially mothers and relatives of the groom look for a bride for him. They search girl and when one is selected, they ask about the family of the girl from her neighbours. If he satisfies with the family, then he sends “*sovchi*”. *Sovchi* means a person who is appointed by the bridegroom to see the adult daughter of a household and ask for her parents’ consent to give her as a bride. [19; 542] And it is translated into English as *matchmaker*. Usually mother and aunts of the bridegroom play a role of the matchmaker in Uzbek culture. They visit to the future bride’s house. If the parents and the girl are agree for this *sovchi*, then parents appoint Fatiha-Tui. It is an engagement party which is celebrated before the wedding day. The relatives of the bridegroom bring *nan* and *patir* to the house of the bride. *Patir* is also one type of the flatbread that is made without yeast, and therefore does not rise. Then the custom named “*Non sindirish*”, which is considered as a rite, is performed in Fatiha-Tuyi. *Non* is broken off pieces and relatives, neighbours, dear people of the both groom and bride take it. It means that the groom and bride are engaged. Fatiha-Tui ends with setting the date of the wedding. [19; 57]

As you know, Uzbek novel “*O’tkan kunlar*” is translated into English by Carol Ermakova and Mark Reese. And there is a passage in the novel when Khasanali and Ziya-shakhichi visit to the house of Kutidor as *sovchi*. The following passage is given in the source language: “*Ziyo aka To’ybekaning yozgan dasturxonini tuzatib, kulchalarni sindirdi.*” [16; 42] The target text of the passage which is translated by Carol Ermakova is as: “*Ziya-shakhichi smoothed the tablecloth Toibeka had laid out and broke off a piece of flatbread.*” [17; 46], while Mark Reese translated it as: “*Ziyo-aka smoothed the tablecloth laid out by Toibeka and broke some bread into pieces.*” [18; 63] *Nan* is given as “*kulcha*” in the source text and translated as bread by both translators. Hospitality of Uzbek people is described here. In Uzbek culture, when a guest visits, the host lays the table and puts the bread on the table at first, then hands it to the guest. The guest breaks off a piece of it and eats.

There are a lot of national ceremonies in Uzbek life. And almost in all of them one can see the importance of the bread, how uzbek people appreciate and show their great respect of *nan* during the ceremonies. As above mentioned, the role of *nan* in Uzbek life is very great. And the custom which is called “*Non sindirish*” is preceded before wedding day in Fatiha-Tui in Uzbek culture.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, it was not easy for the translators to find the anaphor of the uzbek culture-bound words or phrases. The uzbek culture is particularly attractive to learners, whereas it remains to be a challenge because of its profound history and complex background. The linguoculturological analysis of the uzbek culture-specific items show that during the translation process translators prefer to provide a larger amount of the explanation of the non-equivalent words to meet user’s needs. And explicatory translation strategy is considered one of the best way of translating culture-bound words. This translation rewords the meaning into another form for better understanding of the equivalent-lacking word to the receptor. The reason for using this translation is that various background knowledge, difference between the language structures of the target text receptor. Sometimes this translation is called explicitation. And it is the technique of making explicit in the target message information and adds new elements to the structure of the source text while translating them. As a result, a combination of translational equivalents plus explanations which are given in the footnotes and endnotes are the major means adopted by those translation versions. Examples of this method were considered using the target texts of the translation versions of Abdullah Kadiri’s “*O’tkan kunlar*” into English by Carol Ermakova and Mark Reese. Furthermore, the inappropriateness of certain translational equivalents suggests the necessity for a close scrutiny of various aspects in the process of equivalent identification, including culture-specific items of the different language words, necessity of the explanations which are given in the endnotes or footnotes of the equivalents of the culture-bound words in the target language, and cultural connotation of each constituent part of an

equivalent. This leads to a discussion and comparison of equivalent and explanation types and the need to analyse the linguocultures of the various languages. The paper links directly to the linguoculturological analysis of the Uzbek linguocultures which are translated by the professional translators and used explanatory dictionaries of English and Uzbek languages during the analysis in order to explain the further explanation for the readers. Finally, the paper provides some conclusions and perspectives for better improving the cultural dimension of researchers' linguoculturological study of the culture-specific items in the translation process.

References / Iqtiboslar/Сноски

1. Peter Newmark. Approaches to Translation. Pergamon Press. Oxford, New York. 2001. 183 p.
2. Bassnett, Susan & Lefevere, André (eds). 1990. Translation, History and Culture. London: Pinter. 3 p.
3. Nida, Eugene A. 1964. Toward a Science of Translating: With Special Reference to Principles and Procedures Involved in Bible Translating, Leiden: E. J. Brill. 131 p.
4. Mark Shuttleworth & Moira Cowie. Dictionary of Translation Studies. Published 2014 by Routledge. 55 p.
5. Gadamer, H. G. 2004b. Philosophical Hermeneutics. Translated and edited by D. E. Linge. Second edition, Berkeley: University of California Press. 67, 68 p.
6. Mildred L. Larson. Meaning-based translation: a guide to cross-language equivalence. -2nd ed. Copyright 1998 by University Press of America, Inc. Lanham, New York, Oxford. 169 p.
7. Peter Newmark. A textbook of translation. Shanghai foreign language education press. Printed and bound in Great Britain by Wheaton A. & Co. Ltd, Kxeter. 1988. 79 p.
8. Said Faiq. Cultural encounters in translation from Arabic. 2004. Printed and bound in Great Britain. 1 p.
9. Geertz C. The Interpretation of Cultures. London: Hutchinson. 1973. 12 p.
10. Triandis, H.C. The self and social behavior in differing cultural contexts. 1989. 20 p.
11. Maslova, V.A. Linguoculturology. Manual for students. Moscow. 2001. 20 p.
12. Vorobev, V.V. Linguoculturology. Theory and methods. – M., 1997.– B. 44 p.
13. Maslova, V.A. “Conceptual Basics of Modern Linguistics”. Moscow: Flinta Publ., 2019. 332 p.
14. Sapir, E. Selected works on linguistics and cultural studies. – M., 1993.- p. 259.
15. Catford, J. C. A linguistic theory of Translation. Oxford University Press. 1965. 49 p.
16. Abdulla Qadiri. O‘tkan kunlar. Novel. “Sharq”. Tashkent 2018. 35, 322, 221, 57, 58, 226, 42 p.
17. Abdulla Qadiri. Days Gone By. Translated by Carol Ermakova. Karimov foundation. Nouveau Monde editions, 2018. Paris. 39, 287, 199, 60, 206, 17, 61, 46 p.
18. Abdullah Qodiriy. O‘tkan kunlar (Bygone Days). Translated by Mark Reese. Published by Muloqot Cultural Engagement Program. Nashville TN. 2018. 55, 347, 423, 243, 445, 78, 80, 79, 442, 445, 466, 248, 63 p.
19. E. Begmatov, A. Madvaliev, N. Makhkamov, T. Mirzaev, N. Tuxhliev, E. Umarov, D. Khudaiberganova, A. Khojiev. An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 39, 163, 155, 415, 562, 57, 662, 542, 57 p.
20. Lucinda Coventry, Martin Nixon. The Oxford English Minidictionary. Fifth edition, revised. Oxford university press. New York. 2003. 301, 313 p.
21. Zoya Proshina. Theory of Translation. (English and Russian). 3rd edition, revised. Vladivostok Far Eastern University Press. 2008. 109 p.
22. Macmillan English Dictionary for advanced learners. International student edition. First published 2002. Printed in Malaysia. 143, 320, 1430, 301 p.

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